

Compressibility Studies of Tetraalkylammonium Halides in DMSO + Water Mixtures at 298 K

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Compressibility measurements of various tetraalkylammonium halides in DMSO + water mixtures have been made at 298 K using an ultrasonic interferometer. The change in the compressibility behaviour has been discussed in the light of solvent structures and ion solvent interactions. The solvation numbers of the electrolytes have been determined. The single ion solvation numbers have been determined using the 'reference electrolyte' method. The negative solvation numbers in the region 40- to 80 wt% of DMSO have been ascribed to the breakdown of the DMSO + H₂O structures.

The large tetraalkylammonium ions have attracted considerable attention due to the amphipathic nature of the electrolytes. In view of the interesting physical properties, these salts received considerable attention and extensive studies have been made with these salts^{1,2}. However, anomalous behaviour of these salts in different solvents have in no way been resolved and the role of solvents can hardly be explained in the absence of the complete knowledge of the nature of solvation of electrolytes. In the present work, we have studied this aspect using the compressibility method as used by Lahiri and coworkers^{3,4}.

The compressibility measurements of the different tetra-alkylammonium halides (R₄NX where R = CH₃, C₂H₅, C₃H₇ and C₄H₉ and X = Cl, Br or I) have been determined at 298 K in different DMSO + H₂O mixtures (20, 40, 60 and 80% DMSO by weight) using an ultrasonic interferometer at 298 K.

Results and Discussion

The solvation number (*n*) can be obtained by determining the compressibilities of the pure solvent (β_{solvent}) and the ionic solutions (β_{soln}) from the relation⁵,

$$n = \frac{n_s}{n_1} \left(1 - \frac{\beta_{\text{soln}}}{\beta_{\text{solvent}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where *n*, *n*₁ and *n*_s represent the solvation number, number of moles of ions present and assumed to be solvated and number of moles of solvent present in the system of volume *V* respectively.

The acoustic parameters are calculated as follows^{4,6}:

$$\text{Adiabatic compressibility, } \beta = \frac{1}{C^2 \rho}$$

Specific acoustic impedance, $Z = C\rho$

Intermolecular free length, $L_f = k \sqrt{\beta}$

where *k* is the temperature dependent constant, the value of which is taken to be 6.2206×10^4 .

The results (at low and high ionic strengths) are recorded in Tables 1-3.

The velocity of sound in air-free distilled water at 298 K comes out to be $1487 \pm 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ which compares well with the value $1486 \pm 2.3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at 298 K⁶. The velocity *C* (Table 1) increases as the percentage of DMSO in water increases and passes through a maximum in the region 60-80 wt% of DMSO which means that the adiabatic compressibility decreases and passes through a minimum in the same region. Such minima are also observed in other aquo-organic mixtures like methanol + water and ethanol + water^{3,4}. The decrease in compressibility may be due to the fact that the interstitial spaces of water molecules are filled by the organic co-solvent but beyond a certain limit, there cannot be any further accommodation of solvent molecules.

The results are in conformity with the characteristic structural changes associated with the gradual addition of DMSO to water and consequent changes in physical properties of DMSO + H₂O mixtures. The addition of DMSO increases the 3D-polymeric structure of water and the structure formation increases and continues till the maximum is reached

TABLE 1—ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF DMSO + WATER MIXTURES (w/w) AT 298 K

DMSO Wt%	ρ g cm ⁻³	Velocity (C) m s ⁻¹	$10^{13} \beta$ cm ³ /dyne	Z Rayl	<i>L_f</i> Å
0	0.997 07	1 485	45.45	1.481	0.41
20	1.023 47	1 600	38 16	1.638	0.38
40	1.053 57	1 668	34 20	1.775	0.36
60	1.082 56	1 718	31.30	1.860	0.34
80	1.098 05	1 666	32.81	1.829	0.35
100	1.094 10	1 482	41.62	1.621	0.40

TABLE 2—ACCOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF TETRAALKYL-AMMONIUM HALIDES IN DMSO+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

DMSO wt%	ρ g cm ⁻³	Velocity (C) m s ⁻¹	$10^{12} \beta$ cm ² /dyne	$10^{-8} Z$ Rayl	L_t Å	n
Me ₄ Ni (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.027 31	1 610	37.55	1.654	0.383 5	9.0
40	1.056 22	1 678	33.61	1.772	0.360 6	7.0
60	1.085 74	1 728	30.84	1.876	0.345 4	5.0
80	1.102 48	1 685	31.94	1.858	0.351 1	7.0
Et ₄ Ni (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.026 07	1 628	36.95	1.666	0.378 1	15
40	1.056 78	1 680	33.53	1.765	0.360 2	9
60	1.085 38	1 724	30.99	1.871	0.346 3	-34
80	1.101 15	1 684	32.02	1.854	0.351 9	-6
Pr ₄ Ni (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.026 37	1 628	36.94	1.663	0.378 0	23
40	1.056 22	1 694	33.39	1.778	0.359 4	9
60	1.085 18	1 652	33.77	1.792	0.361 5	-25
80	1.100 35	1 646	33.54	1.811	0.360 2	-22
Bu ₄ Ni (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.026 41	1 636	36.40	1.679	0.375 3	30
40	1.056 38	1 676	33.70	1.770	0.361 0	5
60	1.084 15	1 660	33.47	1.800	0.359 9	-22
80	1.099 67	1 648	33.48	1.812	0.359 9	-5
Me ₄ NBr (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.025 46	1 604	37.90	1.645	0.382 9	12
40	1.058 76	1 664	34.23	1.756	0.363 9	-1
60	1.084 51	1 688	32.36	1.830	0.353 8	-11
80	1.100 93	1 636	33.94	1.801	0.362 4	-8
Et ₄ NBr (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.025 55	1 616	37.34	1.657	0.380 1	18
40	1.055 06	1 692	33.11	1.785	0.357 9	12
60	1.084 02	1 648	33.97	1.786	0.362 5	-27
80	1.100 91	1 640	33.78	1.805	0.361 5	-7
Pr ₄ NBr (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.024 96	1 620	37.18	1.660	0.379 3	20
40	1.054 64	1 630	33.56	1.772	0.360 3	6
60	1.083 29	1 656	33.66	1.794	0.360 8	-24
80	1.099 84	1 642	33.73	1.805	0.361 2	-7
Bu ₄ NBr (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.024 61	1 628	36.82	1.668	0.377 4	25
40	1.054 21	1 668	34.09	1.758	0.363 2	0
60	1.082 78	1 660	33.51	1.797	0.360 0	-22
80	1.099 35	1 644	33.66	1.807	0.360 8	-6
Me ₄ NCl (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.023 56	1 628	36.86	1.666	0.377 6	24
40	1.057 46	1 672	39.98	1.780	0.362 6	2
60	1.082 59	1 676	32.88	1.814	0.356 0	-16
80	1.099 75	1 652	33.01	1.817	0.357 4	-1
Et ₄ NCl (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.025 62	1 636	36.43	1.678	0.375 4	29
40	1.056 46	1 630	33.64	1.769	0.360 8	6
60	1.082 50	1 668	33.36	1.866	0.359 3	-21
80	1.099 59	1 646	33.57	1.810	0.360 4	-5
NaI (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.026 89	1 600	38.04	1.643	0.383 6	10
40	1.058 50	1 605	36.72	1.697	0.376 9	-31
60	1.087 46	1 664	33.21	1.810	0.358 4	-20
80	1.104 12	1 640	33.67	1.811	0.360 9	-6
NaBPh ₄ (C=0.05 M)						
20	1.026 61	1 604	37.86	1.646	0.382 7	12
40	1.055 44	1 608	36.64	1.697	0.376 5	-29
60	1.083 70	1 663	33.17	1.808	0.358 2	-19
80	1.099 88	1 648	33.48	1.813	0.359 9	-5

TABLE 3—ACCOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF TETRAALKYL-AMMONIUM HALIDES IN DMSO+WATER MIXTURES (w/w) AT 298 K

C=1.0 M Salt	ρ g cm ⁻³	Velocity m s ⁻¹	$10^{12} \beta$ cm ² /dyne	$10^{-8} Z$ Rayl	L_t Å	n
20% DMSO						
Pr ₄ Ni	1.034 54	1 605	37.52	1.660	0.381 0	2
Bu ₄ Ni	1.034 56	1 608	37.38	1.664	0.380 2	2
Me ₄ NBr	1.031 11	1 610	37.41	1.660	0.380 4	2
Et ₄ NBr	1.030 96	1 612	37.32	1.662	0.379 9	3
Pr ₄ NBr	1.029 17	1 610	37.48	1.657	0.380 7	2
Bu ₄ NBr	1.027 79	1 605	37.77	1.650	0.382 2	1
NaI	1.035 83	1 612	37.15	1.672	0.378 6	3
NaBPh ₄	1.035 30	1 600	37.73	1.669	0.379 2	3
40% DMSO						
Pr ₄ Ni	1.064 78	1 672	33.59	1.780	0.366 4	2
Bu ₄ Ni	1.065 31	1 669	33.69	1.778	0.361 0	1
Me ₄ NBr	1.061 05	1 678	33.47	1.780	0.359 8	2
Et ₄ NBr	1.061 08	1 675	33.59	1.777	0.360 4	2
Pr ₄ NBr	1.059 18	1 673	33.73	1.772	0.361 2	1
Bu ₄ NBr	1.057 38	1 670	33.91	1.766	0.362 2	1
NaI	1.073 42	1 677	33.12	1.800	0.357 9	1
NaBPh ₄	1.062 02	1 670	33.76	1.774	0.361 4	1
60% DMSO						
Pr ₄ Ni	1.091 94	1 720	30.96	1.878	0.346 0	1
Bu ₄ Ni	1.088 28	1 713	31.13	1.870	0.347 0	0
Me ₄ NBr	1.089 66	1 727	30.77	1.882	0.345 0	1
Et ₄ NBr	1.089 94	1 723	30.91	1.878	0.345 8	1
Pr ₄ NBr	1.085 19	1 720	31.14	1.876	0.347 1	0
Bu ₄ NBr	1.083 36	1 719	31.24	1.862	0.347 6	0
NaI	1.093 41	1 731	30.52	1.983	0.343 6	2
NaBPh ₄	1.085 02	1 729	30.85	1.860	0.344 6	1
80% DMSO						
Pr ₄ Ni	1.106 24	1 681	31.99	1.860	0.351 8	2
Bu ₄ Ni	1.103 01	1 673	32.39	1.845	0.353 9	1
Me ₄ NBr	1.108 44	1 684	31.81	1.867	0.351 0	2
Et ₄ NBr	1.107 21	1 682	31.92	1.862	0.351 4	2
Pr ₄ NBr	1.104 46	1 680	32.08	1.855	0.352 3	1
Bu ₄ NBr	1.102 68	1 675	32.32	1.847	0.353 0	1
NaI	1.118 98	1 688	31.36	1.889	0.348 3	4
NaBPh ₄	1.104 07	1 784	31.94	1.859	0.351 4	2

at about 70 wt% of DMSO ($X_{DMSO} \approx 0.35$)⁷⁻¹¹. But here the structure-formation means breakdown of 3D-structure of water associated with the formation of possible DMSO, H₂O complex formation⁷⁻¹¹. The maximum structure-formation can be corroborated from the maximum in the entropy of mixing and viscosity maximum of DMSO+H₂O mixtures $X_{DMSO} \approx 0.35$ (Refs. 10, 11). The spectroscopic studies also indicate maximum interaction of DMSO with H₂O in this region^{12, 13}. Ir and nmr studies¹⁴ also indicate the existence of strong hydrogen bonds between water and DMSO molecules and possible formation of a labile DMSO, 2H₂O complex formation.

The interpretation of the compressibility behaviour of salts in aquo-organic mixtures is extremely difficult and there is a lack of similar data in binary mixtures. It is reasonable to expect that the compressibility values and other acoustic parameters of the tetraalkylammonium salts will show characteristic changes in the region $X_{DMSO} \approx 0.35$. How-

ever, the nature of electrolytes will also influence the compressibility and other values.

It has been observed that the acoustic impedance, in general, decreases as we go from Me_4N^+ to Bu_4N^+ salts and the intermolecular bond length increases slightly. This is reasonable in view of increasing volume as we go from Me_4N^+ to Bu_4N^+ salts.

The tetraalkylammonium ions are characterised by their hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions in aqueous solution. Solubility values of these salts in aqueous solution exhibit peculiar characteristics¹⁵. For chlorides, the solubility is lowest for Et_4NCl , bromides show zigzag behaviour, increases from Me_4NBr to Et_4NBr , decreases for Pr_4NBr but increases again for Bu_4NBr ; for iodide, it increases from Me_4NI to Et_4NI and then decreases. The true explanation is unknown but structure-breaking and structure-making characteristics and polarisabilities of the halide ions may be the reasons for it. Me_4N^+ is a characteristic structure-breaker in water, Et_4N^+ is neither a structure-breaker or structure-maker but Pr_4N^+ and Bu_4N^+ are structure-makers in aqueous solution¹⁶.

Obviously, these properties are responsible for the change in acoustic parameters for different electrolytes in aqueous solutions. The behaviour may change in mixed solvents. Hydrophobic interactions will be absent in organic solvents. However, in mixed solvents both hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions compete for water structure organisation^{16,19}. Hydrophobic effect usually increases with the size of tetraalkylammonium ions being greatest for tetrabutylammonium ion which causes maximum enhancement of solvent structure and usually shift the point of maximum structure formation towards the media richer in water^{16,17}. Anions are regarded as structure-breaker in water, structure-breaking capability decreases with the increase in size of anions. Similarly, anions are less solvated in DMSO and solvating capabilities decrease with increase in size whereas the cations are strongly solvated by DMSO. In $\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures, preferential solvation of cations by DMSO are usually observed and is evident from the extent of solventsorthing occurring in the inner coordination sphere of ions¹¹⁻¹³.

These factors must be responsible for the changes in acoustic parameters of the electrolytes from 40 to 80 wt% of $\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures. It is known that the compressibility measurement can be utilised to determine the solvation number of electrolytes. Generally, compressibility values are determined at various concentrations of electrolytes and extrapolated to zero dilution to calculate the real solvation numbers of electrolytes. Compressibility values of tetraalkylammonium salts in aqueous solutions at low concentrations were determined in our laboratory¹⁸. The hydration numbers of the tetrapropylammonium ion and tetrabutylammonium ion determined from the study are 28 and 30 respectively¹⁸ (assuming the hydration number of Cl ion

to be zero). It has been pointed out that the 'solvation number' of ions changes with increasing concentrations of electrolytes due to cation-cation interactions. The hydration numbers of Me_4N^+ , Et_4N^+ , Pr_4N^+ and Bu_4N^+ have been determined to be 16, 21, 27 and 32 respectively by Pottel and Lossen¹⁹. The values given by Hertz and others^{20,21} are 25, 30, 35 and 40. The values are in agreement with the values reported before.

The results can be rationalised if we analyse the result in terms of limiting molar volume of the cations V^{0+} (which can be related to compressibility). V^{0+} can be written as^{22,23},

$$V^{0+} = V_i^+ + V_e^+ + V_s^+$$

where V_i^+ represents the intrinsic volume of the ions and is positive. V_i^+ should increase from Me_4N^+ to Bu_4N^+ and should be independent on solvent composition. V_e^+ is a negative term arising from electrostriction of the solvent. Electrostriction should decrease with increasing size. However, the change can be regarded to be negligible. V_s^+ is the structural contribution. This is a combination of two opposing effects—a negative contribution arising from the fitting of the ion in a cavity of solvent corresponding to a decrease in volume and a positive contribution arising from the reinforcement of the solvent structure around the ion. In case of tetraalkylammonium ions in aqueous solution, hydrophobic hydration probably outweighs the cavity terms particularly for Pr_4N^+ and Bu_4N^+ ions.

It is to be noted that initially the tetraalkylammonium ions will be highly solvated due to hydrophobic hydration, addition of DMSO causes perturbation and preferential solvation of cations by DMSO molecules which results in the desolvation of the ions releasing solvent molecules free resulting a negative values of the solvation numbers.

One of the limitations of determining the solvation numbers in mixed solvents arises from the fact that the mixed solvent is regarded to be an assorted solvent. The total number of the solvent molecules have been assumed to be equal to the total number of moles of water and DMSO respectively. But if we consider the solvent to be $\text{DMSO} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the solvation number may change.

We have determined the solvation numbers at low and high concentrations of the electrolytes. The results are recorded in Table 4. But the determination of the solvation number of ions are difficult. The usual practice is to assume the solvation numbers of Cl^- , Br^- etc. to be zero. However, we have tried to determine the solvation numbers of ions using the 'reference electrolyte' method. The solvation number of Bu_4NBPh_4 has been determined in the usual way.

$$S_{\text{Bu}_4\text{NI}} + S_{\text{NaBPh}_4} - S_{\text{NaI}} = S_{\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4}$$

The $S_{\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4}$ has been divided equally to give the $S_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}$ or $S_{\text{BPh}_4^-}$. The method has been widely used in determining the equivalent conductance

TABLE 4—SOLVATION NUMBER OF IONS IN DMSO+H₂O MIXTURES AT 298 K AND AT DIFFERENT SALT CONCENTRATIONS

Ion	C=0.05 mol dm ⁻³				C=1.0 mol dm ⁻³			
	DMSO (wt %)							
	20	40	60	80	20	40	60	80
(CH ₃) ₄ N ⁺	-5.0	5.5	-6.5	10.0	1.0	1.5	0.5	0.5
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N ⁺	1.0	8.0	-8.5	9.0	1.0	1.5	0.5	0.5
(C ₃ H ₇) ₄ N ⁺	9.0	7.5	-13.5	-19.0	1.0-2.0	0.5-1.5	-0.5	-0.5
(C ₄ H ₉) ₄ N ⁺	16.0	3.5	-10.5	-2.0	1.0	0.5	-0.5	-0.5
I ⁻	14.0	1.5	-11.5	-3.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.5
Na ⁺	-4.0	-29.5	-8.5	-3.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.5
					2	0.5	1.5	2.5

of ions, viscosity *B*-coefficients of ions etc.^{24,25}. *S*_{BPB}⁻ and the solvation numbers of other ions have been determined in the usual way. The solvation numbers thus obtained are given in Table 4. At higher percentages, negative solvation numbers of tetraalkylammonium ions are observed.

It is apparent that the accurate compressibility data of different electrolytes may be of great help in determining the solvation number of ions in solution which is essential to calculate theoretically the thermodynamics of ion-solvent interactions.

Experimental

The experimental details for the determination of sound velocities are similar to those described in our previous communications^{3,4}.

Tetraalkylammonium halides (Purum or Purise, Fluka) were purified by recrystallisation (at least twice) with appropriate organic solvents²⁶⁻²⁸. The crystallised salts were dried under reduced pressure at the appropriate temperatures. Sodium tetraphenylborate (NaBPh₄) (Puriss, Fluka) was recrystallised from acetone and dried under reduced pressure at 353 K for 72 h. NaI (G.R., Merck) was used without further purification after drying at 413 K.

The purification of DMSO and water was done as described in a previous communication²⁶. The DMSO+H₂O mixtures (20, 40, 60 and 80 by weight % of DMSO) were prepared by mixing the requisite amounts of H₂O and DMSO.

The sound velocities (*C*) were determined with the help of an ultrasonic interferometer manufactured by Mittal Enterprises (New Delhi). The measurements were carried out in a thermostatic bath maintained at 298.15±0.01 K.

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